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Leflunomide is effective against acute myocardial infarction

Research article

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Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

Acute myocardial infarction (AMI) poses a danger, even a fatal one, for many people worldwide. Unfortunately, a safe and highly effective antidote against acute myocardial infarction is still not available.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study investigated whether the dihydroorotate dehydrogenase inhibitor leflunomide can protect people against acute myocardial infarction. New statistical methods were applied.

RESULTS:

The data as provided by the study of Suissa et al. 2006 were re-analysed. The use of leflunomide excludes acute myocardial infarction.

CONCLUSION:

Leflunomide is effective against acute myocardial infarction.

Keywords:

Leflunomide; Acute myocardial infarction; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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1. Introduction

Hoechst Marion Roussel (HMR; now Aventis Pharma) launched leflunomide (HWA-486), a disease-modifying antirheumatic drug (DMARD), in the US in late 1998.¹ Leflunomide is a non-biological novel isoxazole derivative and as a disease-modifying antirheumatic drug mainly used to treat individuals with rheumatoid arthritis, a chronic disease affecting about 0.8% of the population.² Leflunomide is available in oral tablets. The therapy can be started on an oral loading dose of 100 mg once a day for three days. Depending on the patient's tolerance a maintenance dose of 10 mg or 20 mg per day might follow. Leflunomide toxicity need to be treated. Due to the long half-life of leflunomide (approximately 2 weeks), the recommended intervention for wash-out therapy is four grams of cholestyramine every 6 hours for 14 days.³ Discontinuing leflunomide therapy due to concerns for contraindications is indicated. Leflunomide as a very potent dihydroorotate dehydrogenase inhibitor and thereby pyrimidine synthesis inhibitor too,⁴ becomes metabolized in human body to its active form metabolite, also known as A77 1726 or teriflunomide (TERI). Teriflunomide as such acts at the end by inhibiting the mitochondrial enzyme dihydroorotate dehydrogenase.⁵ ·⁶ Dihydroorotate dehydrogenase (DHODH) is rate-limiting enzyme in biosynthesis of pyrimidone. Pyrimidone itself catalyzes the oxidation of dihydroorotate to orotate. Orotate itself is utilized in the biosynthesis of uridine-monophosphate. Theoretically, an inhibition of dihydroorotate dehydrogenase is able to arrest the S-phase in the cell cycle and can potentially slow down the rapid proliferation of (cancer) cells.⁷ In particular, dihydroorotate dehydrogenase (DHODH) is an inner mitochondrial membrane protein which is necessary for linking pyrimidine biosynthesis and the electron transfer of dihydroorotate to ubiquinone in the electron transport chain (ETC).⁸ ⁹ Leflunomide has demonstrated various anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory properties. In particular, leflunomide (Arava, Aventis Pharmaceuticals), an oral pyrimidine synthesis inhibitor, appears to be effective as antiviral agent against Cytomegalovirus, Epstein Barr viurs, Ebola, Influenza, COVID-19¹⁰ and Picornavirus. The de novo biosynthesis of pyrimidine ribonucleotides is supported or determined by the cellular enzyme

¹Kaplan MJ. Leflunomide Aventis Pharma. *Curr Opin Investig Drugs*. 2001 Feb;2(2):222-30. PMID: 11816835.

²Goldenberg MM. Leflunomide, a novel immunomodulator for the treatment of active rheumatoid arthritis. *Clin Ther*. 1999 Nov;21(11):1837-52; discussion 1821. doi: 10.1016/S0149-2918(00)86732-6. PMID: 10890256.

³LiverTox: Clinical and Research Information on Drug-Induced Liver Injury [Internet]. Bethesda (MD): National Institute of Diabetes and Digestive and Kidney Diseases; 2012-. Leflunomide. 2019 Apr 15. PMID: 31644034.

⁴Madak JT, Bankhead A 3rd, Cuthbertson CR, Showalter HD, Neamati N. Revisiting the role of dihydroorotate dehydrogenase as a therapeutic target for cancer. *Pharmacol Ther*. 2019 Mar;195:111-131. doi: 10.1016/j.pharmthera.2018.10.012. Epub 2018 Oct 19. PMID: 30347213.

⁵Fox RI, Herrmann ML, Frangou CG, Wahl GM, Morris RE, Strand V, Kirschbaum BJ. Mechanism of action for leflunomide in rheumatoid arthritis. *Clin Immunol*. 1999 Dec;93(3):198-208. doi: 10.1006/clim.1999.4777. PMID: 10600330.

⁶Fox RI. Mechanism of action of leflunomide in rheumatoid arthritis. *J Rheumatol Suppl*. 1998 Jul;53:20-6. PMID: 9666414.

⁷Madak et al., *Ibid*.

⁸Jones CW. Cytochrome patterns in classification and identification including their relevance to the oxidase test. *Soc Appl Bacteriol Symp Ser*. 1980;8:127-38. PMID: 6269222.

⁹Alexander ED, Aldridge JL, Burleson TS, Frasier CR. Teriflunomide treatment exacerbates cardiac ischemia reperfusion injury in isolated rat hearts. *Cardiovasc Drugs Ther*. 2022 Apr 30:1-6. doi: 10.1007/s10557-022-07341-z. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 35488973; PMCID: PMC9055010.

¹⁰Kaur H, Sharma P, Bhattacharyya A, Sharma S, Chhimpna N, Prajapat M, Prakash A, Kumar S, Singh A, Singh R, Avti P, Thota P, Medhi B. Efficacy and safety of dihydroorotate dehydrogenase (DHODH) inhibitors "leflunomide" and "teriflunomide" in Covid-19: A narrative review. *Eur J Pharmacol*. 2021 Sep 5;906:174233. doi: 10.1016/j.ejphar.2021.174233. Epub 2021 Jun 7. PMID: 34111397; PMCID: PMC8180448.

dihydroorotate dehydrogenase too. Cells acquire pyrimidines, pyrimidines¹¹ themselves are essential cellular metabolites, representing precursor molecules for (viral and non-viral) DNA and RNA biosynthesis.¹² Theoretically, viral replication effectively can be inhibited by targeting the cellular enzyme dihydroorotate dehydrogenase (a novel antiviral principle).¹³ As an example, human cytomegalovirus (HCMV) antiviral therapy is mainly based on inhibitors of viral DNA synthesis, such as ganciclovir (GCV), its prodrug valganciclovir (VGCV), foscarnet (FOS) and cidofovir (CDV). However, anti-cytomegaloviral activity of leflunomide has been studied *in vitro* and *in vivo* for years.^{14, 15, 16, 17} In point of fact, a reactivation of a human cytomegalovirus infection is more and more linked to acute myocardial infarction.^{18, 19, 20, 21} Might leflunomide as such be of any use in this setting?

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

2.1.1. The study of Suissa et al., 2006 (Canada)

Suissa et al.²² conducted a nested case-control study between 1999 and 2003 and found that leflunomide usage is associated with a reduction in acute myocardial infarction (AMI) risk. In toto,

¹¹Rückemann K, Fairbanks LD, Carrey EA, Hawrylowicz CM, Richards DF, Kirschbaum B, Simmonds HA. Leflunomide inhibits pyrimidine de novo synthesis in mitogen-stimulated T-lymphocytes from healthy humans. *J Biol Chem.* 1998 Aug 21;273(34):21682-91. doi: 10.1074/jbc.273.34.21682. PMID: 9705303.

¹²Hyde JE. Targeting purine and pyrimidine metabolism in human apicomplexan parasites. *Curr Drug Targets.* 2007 Jan;8(1):31-47. doi: 10.2174/138945007779315524. PMID: 17266529; PMCID: PMC2720675.

¹³Marschall M, Niemann I, Kosulin K, Bootz A, Wagner S, Dobner T, Herz T, Kramer B, Leban J, Vitt D, Stamminger T, Hutterer C, Strobl S. Assessment of drug candidates for broad-spectrum antiviral therapy targeting cellular pyrimidine biosynthesis. *Antiviral Res.* 2013 Dec;100(3):640-8. doi: 10.1016/j.antiviral.2013.10.003. Epub 2013 Oct 20. PMID: 24149002.

¹⁴Waldman WJ, Knight DA, Lurain NS, Miller DM, Sedmak DD, Williams JW, Chong AS. Novel mechanism of inhibition of cytomegalovirus by the experimental immunosuppressive agent leflunomide. *Transplantation.* 1999 Sep 27;68(6):814-25. doi: 10.1097/00007890-199909270-00014. PMID: 10515382.

¹⁵Waldman WJ, Knight DA, Blinder L, Shen J, Lurain NS, Miller DM, Sedmak DD, Williams JW, Chong AS. Inhibition of cytomegalovirus *in vitro* and *in vivo* by the experimental immunosuppressive agent leflunomide. *Intervirology.* 1999;42(5-6):412-8. doi: 10.1159/000053979. PMID: 10702725.

¹⁶Henaó-Martínez AF, Weinberg A, Waldman WJ, Levi ME. Successful treatment of acyclovir-resistant herpes simplex virus type 2 proctitis with leflunomide in an HIV-infected man. *J Clin Virol.* 2012 Jul;54(3):276-8. doi: 10.1016/j.jcv.2012.02.026. Epub 2012 Mar 31. PMID: 22465339.

¹⁷Gokarn A, Toshniwal A, Pathak A, Arora S, Bonda A, Punatar S, Nayak L, Dwivedi P, Bhat V, Biswas S, Kelkar R, Kannan S, Khattry N. Use of Leflunomide for Treatment of Cytomegalovirus Infection in Recipients of Allogeneic Stem Cell Transplant. *Biol Blood Marrow Transplant.* 2019 Sep;25(9):1832-1836. doi: 10.1016/j.bbmt.2019.04.028. Epub 2019 May 2. PMID: 31054984.

¹⁸Gabrylewicz B, Mazurek U, Ochała A, Sliupkas-Dyrda E, Garbocz P, Pyrlik A, Mróz I, Wilczok T, Tendera M. Cytomegalovirus infection in acute myocardial infarction. Is there a causative relationship? *Kardiol Pol.* 2003 Oct;59(10):283-92. PMID: 14618212.

¹⁹Yousaf Z, Albaz N, Abdelmajid AA, Sabobeh T, Elzouki AN. Reactivation cytomegalovirus leading to acute myocardial infarction- A first reported case in an immunocompetent patient. *Clin Case Rep.* 2021 Feb 10;9(4):1958-1963. doi: 10.1002/ccr3.3914. PMID: 33936622; PMCID: PMC8077325.

²⁰Justo D, Finn T, Atzmony L, Guy N, Steinvil A. Thrombosis associated with acute cytomegalovirus infection: a meta-analysis. *Eur J Intern Med.* 2011 Apr;22(2):195-9. doi: 10.1016/j.ejim.2010.11.006. Epub 2010 Dec 16. PMID: 21402253.

²¹Barukčić, Ilija. (2023). Without cytomegalovirus infection, no brain infarction. *Causation*, 18(12), 5–20. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7574319>

²²Suissa S, Bernatsky S, Hudson M. Antirheumatic drug use and the risk of acute myocardial infarction. *Arthritis Rheum.* 2006 Aug 15;55(4):531-6. doi: 10.1002/art.22094. PMID: 16874796.

only 6/558 AMI cases were under leflunomide therapy while 552/558 AMI cases were not under leflunomide therapy.

Table 1. Leflunomide and acute myocardial infarction (Study of Suissa et al., 2006).

		Acute myocardial infarction		
		YES	NO	
Leflunomide	YES	6	194	200
	NO	552	5386	5938
		558	5580	6138

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = -0,03888389$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00052285
p (EXCL) = 0,99902248
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,97000000
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,98924731

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00052285
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_i) = 0,18000000
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_i) = 0,06451613
P Value (EXCL) = 0,00097704

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/A) \times 100 = (6 / 200) \times 100 = 3,00 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (194 / 200) \times 100 = 97,00 \%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (552 / 5938) \times 100 = 9,30 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (5386 / 5938) \times 100 = 90,70 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (6 / 558) \times 100 = 1,08 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (552 / 558) \times 100 = 98,92 \%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (194 / 5580) \times 100 = 3,48 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (5386 / 5580) \times 100 = 96,52 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (200 / 6138) \times 100 = 3,26 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (5938 / 6138) \times 100 = 96,74 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (558 / 6138) \times 100 = 9,09 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (5580 / 6138) \times 100 = 90,91 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 0,32271739
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,30927835

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 0,30177051
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,67000000

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,87650701
p(IOI)= 0,05832519

2.2. Methods

Avoiding and treatment of logical fallacies addresses one of the most important aspects of any scientific inquiry. Sometimes logically sound definitions are of great help in order to enable us to properly infer **from something known to something unknown**. It also goes without any need of further saying that a definition as such should be logically consistent and correct. However, theoretically, circum-

stances might exist under which it is required to *deal with erroneous definitions*²³ too.

2.2.1. Exclusion relationship

The probability of the exclusion relationship $p(\text{EXCL})$ has been calculated (Barukčić, 2021a,b) and tested for statistical significance. The chi-square goodness of fit test $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | A)$ and $\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | B)$ with one degree of freedom has been used to test whether the sample data published fit the theoretical distribution of an exclusion relationship in the population. Additionally, the P Value has been calculated approximately (see also Barukčić, 2019). The causal relationship k (Barukčić, 2016, 2020, 2021b) has been calculated to evaluate a possible causal relationship between the events. The cumulative, left-tailed hyper-geometric (Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899) distribution (HGD) has been used to test the one-sided left-tailed significance of the causal relationship k . As known, a positive causal relationship would contradict an exclusion relationship and vice versa.

2.2.2. Hyper-geometric distribution

In general, the probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable X is called a hyper-geometric distribution. In contrast to the binomial distribution, the hyper-geometric distribution is characterised by the lack of replacements. In this context, let N denote the population size, let A denote the number of success in the population, let B denote the number of draws (i.e. quantity drawn in each trial), let a itself denote the number of observed successes.

Table 2. Hyper-geometric random variables

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	a	b	A
	A_t	FALSE	c	<u>A</u>
		B	<u>B</u>	N

With this in mind, the probability mass function of the hyper-geometric distribution (see Fisher, 1922; Gonin, 1936; Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Pearson, 1899), denoted as $p(X = a)$, is defined as

²³Strobino, Riccardo, "Ibn Sina's Logic", The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (Fall 2018 Edition), Edward N. Zalta (ed.), URL = <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2018/entries/ibn-sina-logic/>.

$$p(X = a) = \frac{\binom{A}{a} \binom{N-A}{B-a}}{\binom{N}{B}} = \frac{\binom{B}{a} \binom{N-B}{A-a}}{\binom{N}{A}} \quad (1)$$

The hyper-geometric distribution, a probability distribution of a hyper-geometric random variable, has several properties which unfortunately cannot be discussed in detail here. A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is greater than or equal to some specified lower limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (2)$$

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability that the hyper-geometric random variable is less than or equal to some specified upper limit a is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^a \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (3)$$

2.2.3. Fisher's exact test

Fisher's exact test proposed by Fisher (1934) in the fifth edition of *Statistical Methods for Research Workers* (see Fisher, 1934, pp. 99-103) is a statistical significance test which is often used in the analysis of contingency tables while applying the hyper-geometric distribution²⁴. This statistical methodology opens up the possibility to calculate the significance of the deviation from a null hypothesis (e.g., P Value) exactly. Strangely enough, it is common practice to use Fisher's exact test (see also Fisher, 1935) for a sample which is very small. However, it is necessary to point out that Fisher's exact test is valid for all sample sizes without any restriction. Fisher's Exact Test is using the following null and alternative hypotheses:

H0: (null hypothesis)

The two random variables are independent.

H1: (alternative hypothesis)

The two random variables are not independent.

A cumulative hyper-geometric probability denotes whether a hyper-geometric random variable is

²⁴Kim HY. Statistical notes for clinical researchers: Chi-squared test and Fisher's exact test. *Restor Dent Endod.* 2017 May;42(2):152-155. doi: 10.5395/rde.2017.42.2.152. Epub 2017 Mar 30. PMID: 28503482; PMCID: PMC5426219.

greater than or equal to some specified lower limit and less than or equal to some specified upper limit. The P Value of an one-sided right tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \geq a) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{i=a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (4)$$

The P Value of an one-sided left tailed Fisher's exact test is calculated as

$$p(X \leq a) = \sum_{i=0}^{i=a} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \quad (5)$$

2.2.4. The Chi-square goodness of fit test

The χ^2 distribution is one of the most versatile distributions in applied statistics. Historically, the χ^2 distribution has been described by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert (see [Helmert, 1876](#)). Later, the χ^2 distribution has been rediscovered by Karl Pearson (see [Pearson, 1900](#)) in the context of a goodness of fit test. The Chi-square goodness of fit test checks the agreement or conformity or consistency between a hypothetical or a theoretical distribution given in a population and a sample distribution drawn from such a population. Karl Pearson's approximate formula for calculating a Chi-square statistic may be shown schematically as:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{(\text{Observed}_t - E(\text{Observed}_t))^2}{E(\text{Observed}_t)} \quad (6)$$

Some author prefer the use of Yate's correction for continuity (see [Yates, 1934](#)) when there is one degree of freedom.

Example

Let us illustrate the Chi-square goodness of fit test by an example. A random sample of 100 people with 44 men and 56 women is drawn from a certain population. It is assumed that men and women are equal in frequency in the population. The theoretical frequencies of 50 men and 50 women is compared with the observed number of men and women.

Bernoulli trial t	Event	Observed O_t	Expected $E(O_t)$	$(O_t - E(O_t))^2$	$(O_t - E(O_t))^2 / E(O_t)$
1	Men	44	50	36	0.72
2	Women	56	50	36	0.72
Rows = 2		Sample size =	100	Chi-square =	1.44

There are rows - 1 = 2 - 1 = 1 degree of freedom and for $\alpha = 5$ percent level of significance, the rejection region is $\chi^2 \geq 3.84$. A $\chi^2 = 1.44$ is less than 3.84 and not significant. Therefore, we accept the null hypothesis: the sample distribution is consistent with a theoretical distribution given in population. In other words, men and women are more or less equal in frequency in the population. In the case of a necessary condition relationship (SINE), our hypotheses could be:

$$H_0: p(\text{SINE}) \geq 1 \text{ vs. } H_A: p(\text{SINE}) < 1$$

However, a probability cannot be greater than 1. Therefore, the hypotheses are more precisely

$$H_0: p(\text{SINE}) = 1 \text{ vs. } H_A: p(\text{SINE}) < 1$$

Accepting H_0 is equivalent with rejecting H_A and vice versa. Accepting H_A is equivalent with rejecting H_0 . Assumed that the degree of freedom is 1 and for $\alpha = 5$ percent level of significance, the rejection region is $\chi^2 \geq 3.84$. A χ^2 of a necessary condition relationship which is less than 3.84 is not significant. Therefore, we would have to accept the null hypothesis: a sample distribution would be consistent with a theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship given in population. However, Chi-square like any statistics has its limitations. The Chi-square is highly sensitive to sample size. The Chi-square goodness of fit test might give inaccurate results when the sample size is too small ($N < 50$) or too large (see [Bagozzi, 1981](#)) (G-square test). When the sample sizes are too small, Fisher's exact test of independence can be considered too.

2.2.5. The P Value of extreme events

There are circumstances where N Bernoulli trials (see [Uspensky, 1937](#), p. 45) are performed while an event X_t should occur at each single Bernoulli trial t . The probability of a single event is given as

$$p(X_t) = \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t \times p(X_t)}{X_t} \quad (7)$$

The probability of a single anti-event or non-event et cetera is given as

$$p(\bar{X}_t) = 1 - p(X_t) = 1 - \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t}{X_t} - \frac{E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - E(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t - X_t \times p(X_t)}{X_t} = \frac{X_t \times (1 - p(X_t))}{X_t} = \frac{E(\bar{X}_t)}{X_t} \quad (8)$$

As soon, as the number of Bernoulli trials increases, the probability of a single event follows approximately (see Barukčić, 2019, p. 1844) as

$$p(X_t) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{E(X_t)}{N}\right)\right) = \exp\left(-\left(\frac{X_t \times (1 - p(X_t))}{N}\right)\right) \quad (9)$$

Under conditions where $X_t = N$, equation 9 simplifies to

$$p(X_t) = \exp(-(1 - p(X_t))) \quad (10)$$

There are single events or relationships where the probability of an event or of a relationship is constant from trial to trial and equals $p(X_t) = 1$ in the population. Nonetheless, for many reasons, such extreme events like the necessary condition relationship, the sufficient condition relationship, the exclusion relationship et cetera does not necessarily have to be given in a sample drawn from a population too. Under these circumstances, there is a need to proof whether there is a significant difference between the sample probability or proportion and the population probability or proportion or is the difference due to chance. In other words, does the sample probability or proportion deviate significantly from the population probability or proportion which itself is equal to 1. We perform a one-sided left tailed statistical test. A probability of a single event cannot be greater than 1, therefore our hypotheses are:

$$H_0: p(X_t) \leq 0.999\ 999 \dots \text{ vs. } H_A: p(X_t) > 0.999\ 999 \dots$$

In general, the expectation value of extreme events or relationship with $p(X_t) = 1$ at every single Bernoulli trial t is $E(X) = N \times p(X_t) = N \times 1 = N$. Thus far, under circumstances where $N = E(X)$, the hypotheses before simplify to

$$H_0: E(X) \leq N-1 \text{ vs. } H_A: E(X) > N-1$$

However, it is to be noted that $N > N-1$. The cumulative distribution function is given as

$$p(E(X_t))\text{cdf} = p(X_t = 0) + p(X_t = 1) + \dots + p(X_t = (N - 1)) + p(X_t = N) = +1 \quad (11)$$

It is

$$p(E(X_t) \leq N - 1) = p(X_t = 0) + p(X_t = 1) + \dots + p(X_t = (N - 1)) \quad (12)$$

and

$$p(E(X_t) > N - 1) = p(E(X_t) = N) \quad (13)$$

The P Value of a one-sided left (see Barukčić, 2019, p. 1846) tailed statistical test is given as

$$\text{P Value}_{\text{one sided left tailed}} = p(E(X_t) \leq N - 1) = 1 - p(E(X_t) > N - 1) = 1 - \exp\left(-\left(\frac{E(X_t)}{N}\right)\right) \quad (14)$$

We have reasons to believe that a left tailed P Value which is greater than or equal to the significance level α or P Value $\geq \alpha$, is providing some evidence to accept the null hypothesis: The sample distribution deviates significantly from the population distribution. Under such circumstances, the sample data would not support a claim that i.e. there is a significant *conditio sine qua non* relationship or *conditio per quam* relationship or exclusion relationship et cetera. However, a left tailed P Value which is less than the significance level α or P Value $< \alpha$, urges us to reject the null hypothesis and to accept the alternative hypothesis. In other words, there is no deviation of the probability found in a sample distribution from the the probability of a population distribution. It is $p(X_t) = 1$ with a certain P Value.

3. Results

3.1. Leflunomide is effective against acute myocardial infarction

Theorem 1 (Leflunomide is effective against acute myocardial infarction).

H0: (null hypothesis)

Leflunomide is effective against acute myocardial infarction.

H1: (alternative hypothesis)

Leflunomide is not effective against acute myocardial infarction

Proof by the study of Suissa et al. The data of the study of Suissa et al. ²⁵ have been re-analysed (see table 1). The study design of this study of Suissa et al. is more or less appropriate enough for our purposes ($p(\text{IOI}) = 0.05832519$). Furthermore, formally, the data of Suissa et al. are not self-contradictory (causal relationship $k < 0$). Therefore, the proof of an exclusion relationship between the use of leflunomide and acute myocardial infarction is possible. The exclusion relationship between the use of leflunomide and acute myocardial infarction is highly significant ($p(\text{EXCL}) = 0.9990224$; P Value (EXCL) = 0.00097704) while the causal relationship k itself is negative and highly significant too (causal relationship $k = -0.03888389$; P Value (one-sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0.00052285). In the final consequence, the following conclusion appears to be inescapable. The use of the drug leflunomide does exclude acute myocardial infarction. In other words, we accept the null-hypothesis. Leflunomide is an anti-dot against myocardial infarction and does protect people against acute myocardial infarction ($p(\text{EXCL}) = 0.9990224$; P Value (EXCL) = 0.00097704).

□

²⁵Suissa S, Bernatsky S, Hudson M. Antirheumatic drug use and the risk of acute myocardial infarction. *Arthritis Rheum.* 2006 Aug 15;55(4):531-6. doi: 10.1002/art.22094. PMID: 16874796.

4. Discussion

The data of Suissa et al.²⁶ suggests that dihydroorotate dehydrogenase inhibition via teriflunomide might provide protection against acute myocardial infarction. Unfortunately, to date, little is known about the effect of teriflunomide on the human heart. Alexander et al.²⁷ investigated in their study the potential effects of teriflunomide on cardiac ischemia reperfusion injury. Female and male rat hearts were subjected to global ischemia for 25 minutes and reperfusion for 120 minutes. (Langendorff apparatus). Hearts were given teriflunomide for 5 min prior to induction of ischemia and during the reperfusion period and something third. Following ischemia-reperfusion injury, Alexander et al. found an increase in myocardial infarction in teriflunomide treated hearts. The study by Alexander et al. is based on some inaccurate hypotheses. The process by which a global ischemia develops is different and cannot be reduced to only a mechanically induced global ischemia. Leflunomid/teriflunomide act mainly by preventing (virus-induced) thrombosis and not by preventing mechanically induced global ischemia. Furthermore, a therapy with teriflunomide for 5 min prior to induction of global ischemia and during the reperfusion period is too short and is not sufficient to investigate the effect of teriflunomide on global ischemia. Taken all together, the study of Alexander et al. cannot be ignored even if the conclusion of Alexander et al. that teriflunomide treatment might lead to an exacerbation of infarction is neither logically consistent nor justified coherently enough and therefore cannot be accepted. It goes without saying that in this affair further investigations are reasonable, very useful and necessary. Until then, however, and in complete contrast to the Alexander et al. study, we have the epistemic right and the logical duty to base our position on this issue mainly on the data of Suissa et al. (see table 1) and to draw the following conclusion.

5. Conclusion

Provisionally, we may proceed to the following logical conclusion.

‘Leflunomide is effective against acute myocardial infarction.’

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²⁶Suissa S, Bernatsky S, Hudson M. Antirheumatic drug use and the risk of acute myocardial infarction. *Arthritis Rheum.* 2006 Aug 15;55(4):531-6. doi: 10.1002/art.22094. PMID: 16874796.

²⁷Alexander ED, Aldridge JL, Burleson TS, Frasier CR. Teriflunomide treatment exacerbates cardiac ischemia reperfusion injury in isolated rat hearts. *Cardiovasc Drugs Ther.* 2022 Apr 30:1–6. doi: 10.1007/s10557-022-07341-z. Epub ahead of print. PMID: 35488973; PMCID: PMC9055010.

Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

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Associated Data

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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^jhttps://twitter.com/Causation_Journ

^khttps://vixra.org/author/ilija_barukcic

^l<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwf3w1IngcukI00jpw8HTwg>

^m<https://portal.dnb.de/opac/showNextResultSite?currentResultId=%22Barukcic%22%26any¤tPosition=30>